

1 **Inhibition Shapes Acoustic Responsiveness**
2 **in Spherical Bushy Cells**

3
4 *Abbreviated title:* Dynamics of Inhibition in AVCN

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27

28 **Abstract**

29 Signal processing in the auditory brainstem is based on an interaction of neuronal excitation
30 and inhibition. To date we have incomplete knowledge of how the dynamic interplay of both
31 contribute to the processing power and temporal characteristics of signal coding. The spherical
32 bushy cells (SBC) of the anteroventral cochlear nucleus (AVCN) receive their primary excita-
33 tory input through auditory nerve fibers via large axo-somatic synaptic terminals, the endbulbs
34 of Held and additional acoustically driven inhibitory inputs. Spherical bushy cells provide the
35 input to downstream nuclei of the brainstem sound source localization circuitry like the medial
36 and lateral superior olive which rely on temporal precise inputs. In this study, we used jux-
37 tacellular recordings in anesthetized Mongolian Gerbils to assess the effect of acoustically
38 evoked inhibition on the SBCs input-output function and on temporal precision of SBC spiking.
39 Acoustically evoked inhibition proved to be strong enough to suppress action potentials (AP)
40 of SBCs in a stimulus-dependent manner. Inhibition shows slow onset and offset dynamics and
41 increasing strength at higher sound intensities. Additionally, inhibition decreases the rising
42 slope of the excitatory postsynaptic potential (EPSP) and prolongs the EPSP-to-AP transition
43 time. Both effects can be mimicked by iontophoretic application of glycine. Inhibition also
44 improves phase locking of SBC APs to low-frequency tones by acting as a gain control to
45 suppress poorly-timed EPSPs from generating postsynaptic APs to maintain precise SBC spik-
46 ing across sound intensities. The present data suggest that inhibition substantially contributes
47 to the processing power of second order neurons in the ascending auditory system.

48

49

50 **Introduction**

51 The anteroventral cochlear nucleus (AVCN) is part of the first processing station of the central
52 auditory system. Spherical bushy cells (SBCs) located in the rostral pole of the AVCN are
53 constituents of the brainstem sound localization circuitry. These cells receive their main excit-
54 atory input directly from auditory nerve fibers (ANF) by giant synaptic terminals, the endbulbs
55 of Held (Brawer and Morest, 1975; Ryugo and Sento, 1991; Isaacson and Walmsley, 1995;
56 Cao and Oertel, 2010), the activity of which provides suprathreshold excitation (Brawer and
57 Morest, 1975; Schwartz and Gulley, 1978; Ryugo and Sento, 1991; Oertel, 1999; Nicol and
58 Walmsley, 2002). This elaborated axo-somatic synaptic terminal provides the condition to sim-
59 ultaneously record *in vivo* with one and the same electrode (i) the action potentials (AP) of the
60 presynaptic endbulb, (ii) the excitatory postsynaptic potentials (EPSP), and (iii) the action po-
61 tentials of the SBC (originally termed P, A and B by Pfeiffer, 1966; Typlt et al., 2010). The
62 different signal components combined form the complex waveforms of the juxtacellularly rec-
63 orded voltage signals of SBC recordings (Pfeiffer, 1966; Kopp-Scheinflug et al., 2002; Englitz
64 et al., 2009) which can be used to assess the input-output functions of SBCs under acoustic
65 stimulation (Kuenzel et al., 2011; Nerlich et al., 2014). In addition to the ANF input, SBCs
66 receive acoustically triggered inhibitory input mediated by γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA)
67 and/or glycine (Wu and Oertel, 1986; Kolston et al., 1992; Juiz et al., 1996; Mahendrasingam
68 et al., 2004), the function of which is still elusive. The effectiveness of acoustically evoked
69 inhibitory input on SBC responses can be outlined by the fact that not all SBCs show monotonic
70 rate-level functions (RLF) which characterizes their excitatory ANF input (Winter and Palmer,
71 1991; Kopp-Scheinflug et al., 2002), and phase coupling to low-frequency tone bursts is re-
72 duced following the block of inhibitory receptors (Dehmel et al., 2010).

73 In the present study, juxtacellular *in vivo* recordings were used to quantify the temporal and
74 level-dependent interplay of acoustically evoked excitation and inhibition in shaping the acous-
75 tic responsiveness of SBCs. The results show a twofold effect of inhibition which acts as a gain
76 control and increases temporal precision of postsynaptic spike generation. The results empha-
77 size that – like in the somatosensory, the visual and the olfactory system – activity of second
78 order neurons in ascending sensory systems which establish the basis for a multitude of down-
79 stream neuronal processing must be considered as an interplay of excitation and inhibition.
80 Right from the start, inhibition is an integral part of encoded neuronal information.

81 **Methods**

82 *Animals and Surgical Procedure*

83 All experiments were performed at the Neurobiology Laboratories of the Faculty of Bioscience,
84 Pharmacy and Psychology of the University of Leipzig (Germany), approved by the Saxonian
85 District Government, Leipzig (TVV 06/09), and conducted according to the European Com-
86 munities Council Directive (86/609/EEC). Data were collected from 19 subadult Mongolian
87 gerbils (*Meriones unguiculatus*) of either sex aged postnatal day 25–32 (P25–P32). By choos-
88 ing this age range, we considered the prolonged postnatal development of inhibitory transmis-
89 sion in auditory brainstem nuclei (Awatramani et al., 2005; Luján et al., 2008; Friauf et al.,
90 2011).

91 Animals were initially anesthetized by an intraperitoneal injection of a mixture of ketamine
92 hydrochloride (140 µg/g body weight, Ketamin-Ratiopharm[®], Ratiopharm, Ulm, Germany)
93 and xylazine hydrochloride (3 µg/g body weight, Rompun[®], Bayer, Leverkusen, Germany).
94 Supplementary subcutaneous injections of the anesthetic agent at one third of the initial dose
95 were administered approximately every 60–90 minutes to maintain the animal in an areflexic

96 state. During recording sessions, a feedback-controlled heating pad maintained the animal's
97 body temperature at 36.5–37.5 °C. The animal's skull was exposed along the midsagittal line
98 and a metal head post glued onto the bregma point to fix the animal in the stereotaxic device.
99 The hole for the reference electrode was drilled 1.8–2.0 mm caudal from the lambda point at
100 the midline, and the hole for the recording electrode was drilled 1.5 mm lateral to the former.
101 The diameters of the holes were 0.5 mm and 0.8–1.0 mm, respectively. Using this dorsal ap-
102 proach, the recording electrode was lowered into the rostral pole of the anteroventral cochlear
103 nucleus (AVCN) by tilting the animal 12–18° laterally. Glass micropipettes (GB150F-10, Sci-
104 ence Products, Hofheim, Germany) were fabricated with a PC-10 vertical puller (Narishige,
105 Japan) to have impedances of 1–3 MΩ for multi-unit and 7–10 MΩ for single-unit recordings
106 when filled with 3 M KCl.

107 *Multi-barrel recordings*

108 Three-barreled piggyback electrodes (Havey and Caspary, 1980; Dehmel et al., 2010) with the
109 following characteristics were used: tip diameter 4–8 μm, recordings electrode protruding
110 15–25 μm, impedance 5–12 MΩ (GB200F-10 and 3GB120F-10, Science Products). Applica-
111 tion barrels were filled either with glycine (Sigma Aldrich, 100 mM, prepared in 20 mM NaCl,
112 pH 6, buffered with 10 mM HEPES), strychnine hydrochloride (Sigma Aldrich, 2.5 mM, same
113 recipe), or just with the carrier (same recipe but omitting glycine HCL and strychnine HCL);
114 the latter was used for control experiments. Drugs were applied iontophoretically (EPMS 07,
115 npi electronic, GmbH, Tamm Germany) with increasing current steps (drug, +0 to +40 nA;
116 control, +0 to +100 nA). Holding current for each barrel was –15 nA and a channel filled with
117 1 M sodium acetate was used for automatic current balancing.

118 *Acoustic Stimulation*

119 All recordings were performed in a sound-attenuating and electrically isolated chamber (Type
120 400, Industrial Acoustics, Niederkrüchten, Germany) on a vibration-cushioned table. Acoustic
121 stimuli were generated by custom-written MATLAB software (MathWorks, Natick, USA) and
122 digitized at a rate of 97.7 kHz. Signals were presented via custom-made earphones (DT770
123 pro, beyerdynamic, Heilbronn, Germany) and delivered through a plastic tube (length 35 mm,
124 diameter 5 mm) ending just in front of the eardrum.

125

126 *Data Acquisition*

127 Frequency response areas (FRA) were obtained by pseudorandom presentation of pure tones
128 (100 ms in duration, 5 ms \cos^2 ramps, 200 ms interstimulus interval) derived from a predefined
129 matrix consisting of 20 different frequencies equally spaced on a log scale and 10 different
130 sound pressure levels (SPL) equally spaced on a linear scale. Each of these 200 frequency/in-
131 tensity pairs was presented 3–5 times while continuously recording the unit's discharge activ-
132 ity. The FRAs were used to detail each unit's characteristic frequency (CF, the frequency at
133 which the neuron is most sensitive), response thresholds, and, if present, the frequency-inten-
134 sity domain of an inhibitory sideband.

135 For in-depth analyses, repetitive stimulations (100 ms duration, 5 ms \cos^2 ramps, 300 ms in-
136 terstimulus interval, 200–300 repetitions) were carried out (i) at the unit's CF, (ii) within the
137 inhibitory sideband, and (iii) outside of the receptive field (i.e. spontaneous discharge activity).
138 Stimulation loudness was 20–30 dB SPL above the respective threshold.

139

140 *Data Analysis*

141 The rostral pole of the AVCN was targeted considering the tonotopic organization of the nu-
142 cleus described previously (Kopp-Scheinflug et al., 2002; Dehmel et al., 2010). Spherical
143 bushy cells were recognized by their characteristic complex waveform (Pfeiffer, 1966; Winter
144 and Palmer, 1990; Englitz et al., 2009; Typlt et al., 2010) and their primary-like PSTH pattern
145 (Blackburn and Sachs, 1989).

146 The neurons' voltage signals were pre-amplified (Neuroprobe 1600, A-M Systems, Sequim,
147 USA), noise-eliminated (HumBug, Quest Scientific, North Vancouver, Canada), further am-
148 plified (PC1, Tucker-Davis Technologies), and subsequently digitized at a sampling rate of
149 97.7 kHz (24 bit, RP2.1, Tucker-Davis Technologies). Signals were band-pass filtered between
150 50 Hz and 5 kHz using a zero-phase forward and reverse digital IIR filter and stored for offline
151 analysis using custom-written MATLAB software. Recordings were selected for posthoc anal-
152 ysis according to three criteria: (i) standard deviation (AP height) / mean (AP height) < 20 %
153 (data set: 10.6 ± 3.82 , $n = 46$), (ii) uniformity of voltage signals, (iii) signal-to-noise ratio (AP
154 height divided by standard deviation of the baseline) > 12 (data set: 17.8 ± 5.2 , $n = 46$).

155 Juxtacellularly recorded voltage signals of SBCs are typically composed of two (PP-EPSP) or
156 three components (PP-EPSP-AP, Fig. 1) reflecting the discharge of the presynaptic endbulb
157 (PP), the postsynaptic EPSP, and the postsynaptically triggered AP (Englitz et al., 2009; Typlt
158 et al., 2010). Single components were distinguished by means of principal component analysis
159 (Pearson, 1901; Hotelling, 1933) followed by hierarchical clustering. Signals could be grouped
160 into two clusters, one showing the characteristic complex waveform composed of all three
161 components (Fig. 1A and B left) and a second with signals lacking the third component
162 (Fig. 1A and B middle). For reasons of simplicity, the respective signals will be termed (i) *PEA*
163 indicating complexes composed of PP-EPSP-AP and (ii) *PE* indicating PP-EPSP. For *PEA*
164 complexes the inflection point at the rising flank of the second signal component was used to

165 determine the time point of EPSP occurrence by calculating the local minimum of the first
166 derivative preceding the AP maximum. For signals in which the EPSP was temporally sepa-
167 rated from the AP, the first local maximum preceding the AP was taken as the EPSP time point.
168 The EPSP-to-AP transition time was calculated as the time from the occurrence of the EPSP
169 as defined above to the positive peak of the AP component. The average EPSP rising slopes,
170 as related to defined stimulus conditions, were calculated between 20% and 80% of the EPSP
171 amplitudes. Durations of APs were calculated as the time between maximum of the AP and the
172 first local minimum thereafter (Sonntag et al., 2011). For the analysis of pre and postsynaptic
173 phase-locking accuracy, we employed low-frequency stimulation and calculated the vector
174 strength (Goldberg and Brown, 1969) separately for (i) the ANF input, i.e. jointly the time
175 points of EPSPs in the *PE* and *PEA* complexes, (ii) the EPSP, and (iii) the AP of *PEA* com-
176 plexes.

177 *Statistics*

178 Datasets were tested for Gaussianity and equality of variance using the Shapiro-Wilk test
179 (Shapiro and Wilk, 1965) and Levene's test (Levene, 1960), respectively. Student's *t*-test for
180 independent or dependent samples was applied as appropriate. Aggregated data are reported as
181 mean±standard deviation or median [1st quartile, 3rd quartile], respectively. Within-subject
182 comparisons were performed by one-way repeated-measures (RM) ANOVA after testing for
183 sphericity using the Mauchly test (Mauchly, 1940) followed by Bonferroni post hoc tests. Cu-
184 mulative distributions of inter-event intervals were compared using the two-sample Kolmogo-
185 rov–Smirnov test. Correlation between quantities were assessed by Spearman's rank correla-
186 tion (Spearman, 1904) to cover linear and non-linear relationships. For interpretation of all
187 results, a p-value less than 0.05 was deemed significant. Effect size was calculated using the
188 MES toolbox in MATLAB (Hentschke and Stüttgen, 2011) and reported as eta-squared (η^2)

189 for RM ANOVA, Cohen's U1 for two-sample comparisons and most extreme difference (D)
190 for comparisons of cumulative distributions.

191 **Results**

192 This study aimed to evaluate the effects of acoustically evoked inhibition on excitatory auditory
193 nerve fiber-to-spherical bushy cell (ANF-SBC) signal transmission in the anteroventral coch-
194 lear nucleus (AVCN). *In vivo* juxtacellular single-unit recordings were performed while utiliz-
195 ing pure tone stimulation within the unit's high-frequency inhibitory sideband. The response
196 characteristics were compared to the units' spontaneous discharge activity and the activity
197 evoked by acoustic stimulation at the characteristic frequency (CF). Cells were identified as
198 SBCs based on their characteristic complex voltage signals (Fig. 1), which allowed the dis-
199 charge of the endbulb of Held (prepotential, PP) to be differentiated from the excitatory
200 postsynaptic potential (EPSP) and the postsynaptic action potential (AP). While the PP was
201 always followed by an EPSP, some signal complexes lacked the postsynaptic AP (Fig. 1B; see
202 Typlt et al., 2010 for detailed analysis). This three-component distinction is consistent with the
203 P-A-B classification reported previously by Pfeiffer (1966). An additional criterion was the
204 primary-like peristimulus time histogram (PSTH) which characterizes SBCs (Rhode et al.,
205 1983; Blackburn and Sachs, 1989; Typlt et al., 2012).

206 For the stimulation within the inhibitory sideband, we recorded 23 units with low CFs (median
207 [1st quartile, 3rd quartile]: 1.77 [1.39, 2.24] kHz, example in Fig. 2), consistent with the pre-
208 dominant location of large, low-CF SBCs in the rostral AVCN (cat: Tolbert et al., 1982;
209 Rouiller and Ryugo, 1984; Guinea pig: Hackney et al., 1990; Chinchilla: Ostapoff et al., 1994;
210 Monodelphis: Bazwinsky et al., 2008; Mongolian gerbil: Englitz et al., 2009). In the same units,
211 the discharge activity was acquired for stimulation at CF (16/23 units) and outside the receptive

212 field (18/23 units). Another 23 SBCs were recorded ($CF=1.1 \pm 0.3$ kHz) to investigate the effect
213 of inhibition on phase locking. . On average, cells showed spontaneous firing rates biased to-
214 wards mid to high frequencies (49 ± 17 Hz) and thresholds of 13 [6, 17] dB sound pressure
215 level (SPL).

216 Units were classified as having inhibitory sidebands when acoustic stimulation outside the ex-
217 citatory response area resulted in a significant reduction in the spontaneous firing rate ($p < 0.01$,
218 two-sample t-test). For the present investigation we analyzed high-frequency inhibitory side-
219 bands in the range of 4.8 [4, 5.3] kHz with (inhibitory) thresholds of 42.4 ± 15.8 dB SPL
220 (Fig. 2C).

221

222 *The ANF-SBC synapse shows low reliability in vivo*

223 Each unit's spontaneous activity was acquired for periods of 60–120 s in the absence of acous-
224 tic stimulation. Hierarchical clustering of voltage signals (Fig. 1) yielded two distinct types of
225 signals, in the following termed (i) *PEA* (PP-EPSP-AP, Fig. 1B left, black) and (ii) *PE* (PP-
226 EPSP, Fig. 1B middle, gray). In all analyzed cells, this procedure yielded two distinct clusters
227 of these compound signals and no transitional signal complexes in between these two entities.
228 The analysis yielded 97.2% to 99.2% of the triggered events to be sorted in either of the two
229 signal categories. The first two components of both complex voltage signals were similar in
230 shape, suggesting that the *PE* compounds are indicative of signals in which the EPSPs failed
231 to trigger a postsynaptic AP (Fig. 1B, middle). The additional occurrence of the postsynaptic
232 AP establishes the *PEA* compound. Based on the observation that both complex signals shared
233 the first two components, their co-occurrence (*PE+PEA*) was considered the auditory nerve
234 input to the recorded SBC.

235 In all units, both *PE* and *PEA* signals were recorded during spontaneous activity, but their
236 proportion varied greatly between different units. Quantified as failure fraction
237 ($PE/[PE+PEA]$), the mean incidence of the complex signals lacking APs amounted to
238 $25.8 \pm 12.5\%$ and varied between 4.5% and 46.9%. To test for potential presynaptic effects on
239 synaptic transmission reliability, we compared the size of the PPs in *PE* and *PEA* signals in
240 units with sufficiently high signal-to-noise ratios to clearly identify the prepotential ($n = 19$).
241 The comparison yielded no significant difference in average PP size ($PE = 0.16 \pm 0.17$ mV vs.
242 $PEA = 0.17 \pm 0.19$, $p = 0.84$, paired t test, $n = 19$, $U1 = 0.08$), which suggests that postsynaptic
243 spike failures are not likely attributable to the varying convergence of presynaptic inputs (see
244 Discussion for a consideration of this issue). However, EPSPs that triggered APs (*PEA*) and
245 those that did not (*PE*) showed discernible differences with respect to the EPSP rising slopes;
246 the average EPSP rising slopes were calculated between 20% and 80% of the EPSP amplitudes.
247 According to Kuenzel and coworkers, this measure is a reliable *in vivo* estimate of EPSP
248 strength (Kuenzel et al., 2011). In the present study, the EPSP slopes were systematically shall-
249 lower in *PE* compared to *PEA* complexes ($PE = 2.06 \pm 0.4$ V/s vs. $PEA = 2.9 \pm 0.7$ V/s,
250 $p < 0.001$, paired t -test, $n = 23$, $U1 = 0.47$, Fig. 1B, right).

251

252 *Frequency and intensity-specific effects of inhibition*

253 For each cell, the frequency response area (FRA) was analyzed both jointly and separately for
254 the *PE* and *PEA* complexes to quantify how acoustically evoked inhibition shapes both, the
255 intensity and frequency response profiles of SBCs. The sum of the *PE* and *PEA* complexes
256 (Fig. 2A, red and black) was considered the ANF input to the recorded SBC. Figure 2B shows
257 an example of the respective FRA with a mean spontaneous activity of 74 spikes/s, a typical v-
258 shaped area of excitation with a maximum discharge rate of 264 spikes/s at the highest stimulus

259 intensity, and a clearly defined CF at 1.9 kHz with a threshold value of -3 dB SPL. The FRA
260 calculated from the *PEA* complexes, indicating the SBC output signaling, differed considerably
261 with respect to spike rates, as did the frequency and intensity response profiles (Fig. 2C). Spon-
262 taneous discharge activity was lower (43.9 spikes/s), as were the spike rates in the excitatory
263 response area (maximum 156.1 spikes/s). Maximum discharge rates were reached at stimulus
264 intensities of 40 dB SPL and were reduced at higher and lower intensities. The most prominent
265 difference was the occurrence of a coherent frequency-intensity area adjacent to the high-fre-
266 quency border of the excitatory response area where SBC spiking was reduced to levels below
267 that for spontaneous activity forming a high-frequency inhibitory sideband. The present anal-
268 ysis focused on units characterized by such inhibitory sidebands which constitute about 60%
269 of the low-frequency SBCs (Typlt et al., 2012). In our sample, the reduction in postsynaptic
270 AP firing was most prominent 1.4 ± 1.1 octaves above the units' CFs and was always accom-
271 panied by a significant increase in the failure fraction (Fig. 2D) ($p < 0.001$, one-way RM
272 ANOVA, Greenhouse-Geisser corrected, $n = 23$, $\eta^2 = 0.83$, Spont = $22.1 \pm 13.7\%$ vs.
273 CF = $45.4 \pm 16.3\%$: $p < 0.001$; Spont vs. Inh = $67.4 \pm 15.3\%$, $p < 0.001$).

274

275 *Effect of inhibition differs across the frequency response area*

276 Repetitive acoustic stimulation (100 ms tone bursts, 400 ms interstimulus intervals, 200–300
277 repetitions) was used to quantify the dynamics of the units' excitatory and inhibitory responses.
278 As exemplified in Fig. 3, acoustic stimulation outside of a unit's receptive field (0.15 kHz,
279 50 dB SPL; mark on 'Sp' line in Fig. 2, same cell as in Fig. 2) did not change the overall input
280 or the incidence of *PE* or *PEA*. In the dot raster display in Fig. 3A, the whole of *PE* and *PEA*
281 – symbolized by red and black dots, respectively – shows the input to the SBC, and their uni-
282 form distribution indicates that the acoustic stimulation did not change the discharge rate or the

283 proportion between the two signal types. This is illustrated in the upper panel of Fig. 3A high-
284 lighting stimulus onset and offset. The histogram in Fig. 3B shows that the rate of the input to
285 the SBC ($PE + PEA$, gray line) underwent some fluctuations, as did the incidence of SBC APs
286 (black) and AP failures (red), but the rates were not affected by the stimulus. Additionally,
287 normalization of the rates of the two signals to the overall input showed no significant varia-
288 tions (Fig. 3C). During the 200 stimulus repetitions, short-term fluctuations in the incidence of
289 spike failures in the range of 0 to 0.3 were observed. However, these instantaneous changes
290 were not correlated with the stimulus onset or offset (Fig. 3C). To verify that the patterns of
291 occurrence of events is not influenced by acoustic stimulation, we compared the cumulative
292 distribution of inter-event intervals during stimulation (5–95 ms) and spontaneous activity
293 (150–230 ms) and did not find any differences ($ISI_{\text{Spont}} = 20 \pm 17.2$ ms vs.
294 $ISI_{\text{Stim}} = 18.2 \pm 13.6$ ms, $p = 0.65$, two-sample Kolmogorov–Smirnov test, $D = 0.06$).

295 To test the influence of neuronal inhibition on spontaneously occurring spike failures, we rec-
296 orded from SBCs using piggy-back electrodes and applied the glycine antagonist strychnine
297 (2.5 mM, pH 6). While reliably blocking the effect of co-applied glycine, sole application of
298 strychnine had neither an effect on AP rate nor on the ratio between the overall input ($PE+PEA$)
299 and postsynaptic APs (PEA) (data not shown).

300 Acoustic stimulation at the unit's CF 20–30 dB above the threshold (mark at 'CF' in Fig. 2,
301 same cell as in Fig. 2) strongly increased the incidence of both PE and PEA (Fig. 4A, lower
302 panel). It is striking that this stimulation not only triggers a jump in AP rates, but also an in-
303 crease in the rates of AP failures. The blow-ups of the stimulus onset and offset periods eluci-
304 date additional response characteristics (Fig. 4A, upper panel): (i) at the onset of the tone burst,
305 the PEA rates grow faster than the PE rates, (ii) PE rates predominate towards the end of the
306 stimulus, and (iii) during the period of poststimulus rate depression, both signal types occur,
307 albeit with reduced incidence.

308 Binning the events in a PSTH emphasizes the dynamics of the respective changes (Fig. 4B).
309 The overall input to the SBC (Fig. 4B gray line, $PE + PEA$) and the postsynaptic AP activity
310 (black line, PEA) shows a robust stimulus-evoked absolute rate increase. Both activities display
311 the primary-like response patterns typical of tone burst-triggered ANF and SBC recordings.
312 Additionally, the recordings yielded a pronounced absolute increase in the PE rate (Fig. 4B,
313 red line), indicating that, while the acoustically evoked ANF excitation on SBCs is strongly
314 increased, additional physiological processes limit the postsynaptic spike generation. Still, the
315 increase in postsynaptic APs and AP failures followed very different time courses at stimulus
316 onset. Starting with a delay of about 3 ms, $PE+PEA$ and PEA rates increased steeply to form
317 the characteristic phasic onset of the primary-like response pattern. With a slightly longer delay
318 of about 4 ms, the rates of AP failures (PE) also increased, though with a lower growth rate.
319 This increase in AP failures occurs during the transition phase from the excitatory onset peaks
320 towards the respective sustained response levels (gray and black lines in Fig. 4B). Conse-
321 quently, the onset peak of the PEA histogram shows a sharper decay than the peak of the input
322 activity. The increase in the AP failure rate continues for about 20 ms after stimulus onset
323 outlasting the onset peak of the primary-like PSTH. This is evidenced by normalizing the PE
324 and PEA rates to the SBC input ($PE+PEA$; Fig. 4C) which shows that CF stimulation caused
325 a substantial increase in AP failures. In the present example (and in 5/16 recorded units) the
326 incidence of AP failures during CF stimulation surpassed the incidence of APs. Significant
327 increases in AP failures during CF stimulation were found in 13/16 recorded SBCs, albeit with
328 different failure rates. During the subsequent sustained phase of the PSTH up to the stimulus
329 offset, a continuous gradual increase in PE probability at the expense of PEA complexes was
330 observed (Fig. 4C). Because of the almost complete post-stimulus suppression of neuron spik-
331 ing, it is difficult to judge the dynamic changes between PE and PEA signals at the stimulus

332 offset (Fig. 4C, dashed lines). The recording indicates that 50–100 ms passed before the unit
333 resumed the pre-stimulus level of spontaneous activity (Fig. 4A, B).

334 An overall assessment of SBC discharge activity during CF stimulation suggests that in addi-
335 tion to the strong excitation, other stimulus-triggered physiological mechanisms reduce neu-
336 ronally spiking. To test if postsynaptic depression contributes to the increase in spike failures,
337 the inter-event interval distributions were analyzed. A respective reduction would indicate the
338 potential impact of depression. Indeed, during CF stimulation, the distribution of inter-event
339 intervals of *PE* signals was shifted towards lower values ($ISI_{\text{Spont}} = 20.7 \pm 16$ ms vs.
340 $ISI_{\text{Stim}} = 5.5 \pm 3.9$ ms, $p < 0.001$, two-sample Kolmogorov–Smirnov test, $D = 0.59$) suggesting
341 that postsynaptic depression contributes to the increase in spike failures. However, the effec-
342 tiveness of depression in preventing AP spiking was shown to be low compared to that of
343 inhibition (Kuenzel et al., 2015).

344 As presently shown and also reported by Kuenzel and coworkers, acoustic stimulation at the
345 unit's CF triggers superposed effects of excitation and inhibition on SBC activity (Kuenzel et
346 al., 2011) which made it difficult to draw differentiating conclusions from the above analysis.
347 To dissect the effects of such interactions on the recorded activity, we employed pure-tone
348 stimulation within the unit's high-frequency inhibitory sideband ('Inh' in Fig. 2; Fig. 5, same
349 cell as in Fig. 2). Such stimulation did not change the ANF input to SBCs, as indicated by the
350 overall steady rate of input to the SBC before, during, and after tone burst presentation
351 (*PE* + *PEA*, Fig. 5A, red and black dots; Fig. 5B, gray line) or the inter-event intervals
352 ($ISI_{\text{Spont}} = 20.6 \pm 16.8$ ms vs. $ISI_{\text{Stim}} = 19.6 \pm 15.7$ ms, $p = 0.79$, two-sample Kolmogorov–
353 Smirnov test, $D = 0.03$). This demonstrates that there was no stimulus evoked excitatory drive
354 on the SBC, and the observed overall activity can be regarded as the unit's spontaneous dis-
355 charge activity. Still, the acoustic stimulation had a prominent effect on SBC activity. It caused
356 an enduring reduction in postsynaptic APs (Fig. 5A), i.e. *PE* complexes greatly outnumbered

357 *PEA* complexes after stimulus onset (Fig. 5A, upper left panel), while *PEAs* again prevailed
358 after stimulus offset (Fig. 5A, upper right panel). The histogram shows that *PEA* reduction is
359 matched with respect to both, dimension and temporal dynamics by an increase in *PEs*
360 (Fig. 5B, C). For stimulation within the inhibitory sideband as compared to CF stimulation, the
361 *PEA* reduction occurs earlier and proceeds faster. After stimulus offset, the release from reduc-
362 tion lasts for about 10 ms (Fig. 5C). Unlike for CF stimulation, there was neither a general
363 activity-reducing aftereffect of acoustic stimulation nor enduring modifications of the *PE/PEA*
364 ratio.

365 To evaluate whether the data of the exemplary unit provides a valid description of the impact
366 of excitatory and inhibitory stimulation on AP reduction in SBC, a summary analysis was per-
367 formed. For that, the PSTHs for all units recorded under the different stimulus conditions were
368 calculated and averaged across cells (Fig. 6). Similar to the exemplary unit, the activity outside
369 the acoustic response area ($n = 18$, indicated as ‘stimulus 2 oct < CF’), at the units’ CFs
370 ($n = 16$, ‘CF stimulus’), and within the high-frequency inhibitory sidebands ($n = 23$, ‘Inh stim-
371 ulus’) were compared. Acoustic stimulation outside the acoustic response area did not affect
372 the overall input to the SBC (Stim (10–90 ms) = 56.1 ± 15.4 Hz vs. Spont
373 (150–230 ms) = 56.9 ± 16 Hz $p = 0.34$, paired *t*-test, $U_1 = 0.08$, $n = 18$, Fig. 6A, upper panel)
374 or the failure fraction (10–90 ms vs 150–230 ms, Stim (10–90 ms) = $25.3 \pm 17.3\%$ vs. Spont
375 (150–230 ms) = $25.5 \pm 16.9\%$, $p = 0.85$, paired *t*-test, $U_1 = 0.08$, $n = 18$, Fig. 6A, lower panel).
376 Acoustic stimulation at the units’ CFs resulted in PSTHs displaying primary-like response pat-
377 terns of the ANF input to the SBCs (Fig. 6B, upper panel, Stim (10–90 ms) = 212.4 ± 75.4 Hz
378 vs. Spont (150–230 ms) = 69.3 ± 38.7 Hz, $p < 0.001$, paired *t*-test, $U_1 = 0.86$, $n = 16$) as well
379 as the SBC AP discharges (data not shown). However, the reliability of signal transmission at
380 the ANF-SBC synapse decreased during CF stimulation, as shown by the higher failure fraction
381 with slow onset dynamics (Stim (10–90 ms) = $43.3\% \pm 17.5\%$ vs. Spont (150–

382 230 ms) = $30.4 \pm 17.5\%$, $p < 0.01$, paired t -test, $U1=0.13$, Fig. 6B, lower panel) and a gradual
383 increase throughout the continuous stimulation (25–90 ms, $r_s = 0.57$, $p < 0.001$). When cells
384 were stimulated within their inhibitory sideband, no change in SBC input was observed (Stim
385 (10–90 ms) = 68.7 ± 36.4 Hz vs. Spont (150–230 ms) = 71.2 ± 39.7 , $p = 0.29$, $U1 = 0.07$,
386 paired t -test, $n = 23$, Fig. 6C, upper panel). However, the incidence of AP failures increased
387 considerably and surpassed the probability of AP generation (Stim (10–90 ms) = $58.1 \pm 16.8\%$
388 vs. Spont (150–230 ms) = $26.1 \pm 12.7\%$, $p < 0.001$, paired t -test, $U1 = 0.61$, $n = 23$, Fig. 6C
389 lower panel). The increase in failure fraction showed slow onset and offset dynamics and a
390 decrease with continuing stimulation (25–90 ms, $r_s = -0.57$, $p < 0.001$).

391 *Inhibition is delayed relative to excitation, and persists after stimulation ceases.*

392 For an in-depth analysis of the time course of the onset and offset of acoustically evoked exci-
393 tation and inhibition, PSTH data for all recorded cells were averaged (Fig. 7). The time course
394 of the increase in the AP failure fraction at stimulus onset was compared to the time course of
395 stimulus-evoked AP firing. For the failure fraction, stimulation within the inhibitory sideband
396 showed slow onset dynamics (thin red lines, data from the different units) with an average half-
397 rise time (HRT) of 8.4 ms (onset of stimulation to 50% of failure fraction; Fig. 7, lower left,
398 thick red line). The respective increase in average AP firing triggered by CF stimulation was
399 considerably faster (HRT = 4 ms, black line). In addition, after the end of the acoustic stimu-
400 lation, the dynamics of release from inhibition differed considerably from the reduction of CF-
401 triggered AP firing (Fig. 7, lower right). When fitting a mono-exponential function of the form
402 $A \cdot e^{(-x/\tau)} + c$ to the data, the failure fraction showed a tenfold slower decay ($\tau_{\text{Inh}} = 9.38$ ms,
403 95% confidence interval: [8.9, 9.8] ms) for the release from inhibition than for the offset of
404 excitation ($\tau_{\text{Ex}} = 0.86$ ms, 95% confidence interval: [0.67, 1.06] ms).

405

406 *The strength of inhibition depends on stimulus intensity*

407 The auditory system works along five orders of magnitude with respect to intensity, with sound
408 intensity being encoded by the spike rate (Sachs and Abbas, 1974; Palmer and Evans, 1980;
409 Winter et al., 1990). Here, we tested whether the strength of acoustically evoked inhibition also
410 directly depends on sound intensity at the first processing stage of the central auditory system.
411 As done before, we analyzed rate-level functions (RLFs) under three different conditions: (i)
412 outside the receptive field, (ii) at the CF, and (iii) within the inhibitory sideband. Figure 8A-C
413 shows the respective analysis for the exemplary unit shown in Fig. 2. Acoustic stimulation
414 outside the receptive field ('SP', dotted line; see also respective line in Fig. 2) did not change
415 the overall input ($PE+PEA$, Fig. 8A) or the AP firing (PEA , Fig. 8B) of the SBC, resulting in
416 a stable failure fraction (Fig. 8C). When stimulating at CF, the overall input rate monotonically
417 increased up to a level of 40 dB SPL and showed constant firing towards higher SPLs ('CF',
418 solid line, Fig. 8A). Such monotonicity of the input activity was found in all 23 recordings.
419 However, the RLFs of SBC AP firing differed considerably from the input activity. Of the 23
420 units, 12 showed pronounced non-monotonic RLFs, defined as a minimum 20% decrease of
421 postsynaptic firing at high stimulus levels ('CF' in Fig. 8B for the exemplary unit). Corre-
422 spondingly, the failure fractions in the units with non-monotonic RLFs were markedly in-
423 creased at high stimulus levels (Fig. 8C). For stimulation within the inhibitory sideband, alter-
424 ing the stimulus level did not affect the overall input ('Inh', dashed line) (Fig. 8A), but did
425 result in monotonously decreased SBC firing with increasing stimulation intensity (Fig. 8B),
426 which was accompanied by a steadily increasing failure fraction (Fig. 8C). All analyzed cells
427 ($n = 23$) showed decreased SBC firing within the inhibitory sideband (-10 to 0 dB
428 SPL = 48 ± 16.1 Hz vs. $70-80$ dB SPL = 18.9 ± 12 Hz, $p < 0.001$, paired t-test, $U1 = 0.61$,
429 $n = 23$), and a corresponding increase in the failure fraction (-10 to 0 dB SPL = 22.5 ± 14.2 Hz

430 vs. 70–80 dB SPL = 68 ± 14.2 , $p < 0.001$, paired t -test, $U1 = 0.83$, $n = 23$, Fig. 8D). The effi-
431 ciency of acoustically triggered AP inhibition correlated with the level of acoustic stimulation
432 in a unit-specific manner and amounted to spontaneous AP rate reductions by 19 to 94 % at
433 70–80 dB SPL tone burst intensity. The absolute increase in failure fraction across units varied
434 between 8% and 77% and was negatively correlated with the units' spontaneous failure frac-
435 tion, i.e., units with lower spontaneous failure fractions showed higher absolute increase during
436 inhibitory stimulation ($r_s = -0.52$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 23$). For stimulation within the inhibitory side-
437 band, both, the decrease in SBC firing (Fig. 8D, left) and the increased PE probability (Fig.
438 8D, right) were correlated with the stimulus intensity (APs: $r_s = -0.59$, $p < 0.001$; failure frac-
439 tion: $r_s = 0.7$, $p < 0.001$, $n = 23$).

440 *Inhibition reduces EPSP strength and increases EPSP-to-AP transition time*

441 Previous *in vivo* studies showed that within the cochlear nucleus, the duration of juxtacellularly
442 recorded action potentials can vary between recorded cell types (Mongolian gerbils: Typlt et
443 al., 2012). Additionally, the synaptic transmission delay is progressively reduced during early
444 postnatal development (mice: Sonntag et al., 2011), while in adults the transmission delay be-
445 comes prolonged with increasing discharge rates (Mongolian gerbils: Tolnai et al., 2009). Here,
446 we tested whether acoustically evoked inhibition also shapes the AP waveform and affects the
447 timing of synaptic transmission. We analyzed APs recorded during spontaneous activity and
448 during inhibitory stimulation. For each recording, 4405 ± 1767 APs were analyzed, and the
449 relevant parameters could be extracted from $98.7 \pm 1.5\%$ of all APs. Under both stimulus con-
450 ditions, the EPSP-AP transition times were similarly correlated with the EPSP rising slopes
451 (Spont: $r_s = 0.43$, $p < 0.001$, Inh: $r_s = 0.41$, $p < 0.001$, data not shown, but see Kuenzel et al.,
452 2011; Nerlich et al., 2014) while displaying considerable within-unit variability (Fig. 9Ai, Aii).
453 A Boltzmann function of the form $1/(1 + e^{-\tau(x-d)})$ was fitted to the cumulative distribution

454 with decay constant τ and symmetric inflection point d ($R^2 > 0.99$). Under acoustically evoked
455 inhibition the shape of the distribution stayed constant, but the EPSP-AP transition times were
456 shifted towards higher values (Fig. 9Aii). In all cells analyzed, inhibitory stimulation shifted
457 the median EPSP-AP transition time towards higher values (Spont = $236 \pm 17 \mu\text{s}$ vs.
458 Inh = $249 \pm 17 \mu\text{s}$, $p < 0.001$, paired t test, $U1 = 0.28$, $n = 23$, Fig. 9Aiii).

459 The strength of the EPSPs was estimated by their rising slopes (Fig. 9Bi). Acoustically evoked
460 inhibition reduced EPSP strength and shifted the cumulative distribution towards lower EPSP
461 rising slopes (Fig. 9Bii). This was a small, but robust effect observable in 19/23 cells
462 (Spont = $2.8 \pm 0.7 \text{ V/s}$ vs. Inh = $2.7 \pm 0.6 \text{ V/s}$, $p < 0.001$, paired t -test, $U1 = 0.06$, $n = 23$,
463 Fig. 9Biii).

464 Also, steeper EPSP rising slopes were correlated with shorter AP durations, both under the
465 conditions of spontaneous activity as well as during acoustic stimulation of inhibition (Spont:
466 $r_s = -0.26$, $p < 0.001$; Inh: $r_s = -0.27$; $p < 0.001$, data not shown). As described above, inhibi-
467 tory stimulation caused more shallow EPSPs, but under these conditions the AP durations were
468 still shorter than the respective APs during spontaneous activity (Spont = $0.43 \pm 0.07 \text{ ms}$ vs.
469 Inh = $0.41 \pm 0.06 \text{ ms}$, $p < 0.001$, paired t -test, $U1 = 0.04$, $n = 23$).

470 *Temporal precision of SBC firing surpasses that of its excitatory input*

471 Joris and colleagues hypothesized an increase of temporal precision in spike timing from the
472 auditory nerve to bushy cells based on a population comparison of ANF and BC recordings
473 partly mediated by inhibitory inputs (Joris and Smith, 2008). Dehmel et al. (2010) observed a
474 decrease in phase locking when pharmacologically blocking the inhibition. Here we aim at an
475 immediate comparative analysis of phase locking of the SBCs' pre- and postsynaptic activity
476 which is necessary to draw conclusions about the mechanisms that cause these improvements.
477 To test if the temporal precision is improved at the level of the SBCs compared to the ANF,

478 we calculated the vector strength during low-frequency stimulation (0.94 ± 0.2 kHz,
479 min = 0.5 kHz, max = 1.2 kHz, n = 23) separately for the following activities: (i) ANF input,
480 i.e. EPSP time points in both *PE* and *PEA* complexes, (ii) the respective EPSP time points of
481 the *PEA* complexes, and (iii) AP time points of the respective signals. Twenty-three units that
482 showed a significant degree of phase locking ($p < 0.001$, Rayleigh test) at the level of the SBC
483 action potentials were included in the analysis (Fig. 10). The overall analysis shows a highly
484 significant increase in the vector strength from the ANF input to the SBC APs ($p < 0.001$, RM
485 ANOVA, Greenhouse-Geisser corrected, $\eta^2 = 0.36$, Fig. 10A). The phase locking of the EPSPs
486 differed from that of the APs ($\text{EPSP}_{\text{succ}} = 0.61 \pm 0.07$ vs. $\text{AP} = 0.65 \pm 0.07$, $p < 0.001$, Bonfer-
487 roni post-hoc test, $U1 = 0.34$) and furthermore differed depending on whether the EPSPs pre-
488 ceded an AP or not ($\text{EPSP}_{\text{fail}} = 0.53 \pm 0.08$ vs. $\text{EPSP}_{\text{succ}} = 0.61 \pm 0.07$, $p < 0.001$, Bonferroni
489 post-hoc test, $U1 = 0.3$). While the EPSPs of *PE* complexes showed a vector strength similar
490 to the ANF input ($\text{ANF} = 0.51 \pm 0.1$ vs. $\text{EPSP}_{\text{fail}} = 0.53 \pm 0.08$, $p = 0.59$, Bonferroni post-hoc
491 test, $U1 = 0.04$), the temporal precision was substantially increased in EPSPs that triggered an
492 AP ($\text{ANF} = 0.51 \pm 0.1$ vs. $\text{EPSP}_{\text{succ}} = 0.61 \pm 0.07$, $p < 0.001$, Bonferroni post-hoc test,
493 $U1 = 0.41$). In follow-up analyses, the EPSP rising slope was used as an estimate of the EPSP
494 strength. For each unit, EPSPs were sorted according to their rising slope and the vector
495 strength calculated for large EPSPs (top 20% of the rising slopes) and small EPSPs (bottom
496 20%). Large EPSPs showed a considerably better phase locking than small EPSPs (EP-
497 $\text{SP}_{\text{small}} = 0.56 \pm 0.06$ vs. $\text{EPSP}_{\text{large}} = 0.62 \pm 0.06$, $p < 0.001$, paired *t*-test, $U1 = 0.29$, $n=23$, data
498 not shown) and are more likely to generate a postsynaptic AP ($P_{\text{small}} = 0.31 \pm 0.23$ vs
499 $P_{\text{large}} = 0.83 \pm 0.11$, $p < 0.001$, paired *t*-test, $U1 = 0.7$, $n = 23$, data not shown). An even greater
500 improvement in phase locking was observed for the AP ($\text{EPSP}_{\text{large}} = 0.62 \pm 0.06$ vs.
501 $\text{AP} = 0.65 \pm 0.07$, $p < 0.001$, Bonferroni post-hoc test, $U1 = 0.14$, $n = 23$). To investigate, if the

502 improvement of AP phase locking can be accounted for by the variability in EPSP-to-AP trans-
503 mission times, we correlated the latter with the phase position of successful, i.e. AP preceding
504 EPSPs. For normalization of the phase angles between units, the maxima of the EPSP histo-
505 grams were centered around 180 degrees of the respective stimulus period. In all cells analyzed,
506 the EPSP-to-AP transition was negatively correlated to the time point within the stimulus cycle
507 (Fig. 10B, $-0.53 < r_s < -0.19$, $p < 0.001$), i.e. events that occurred early in the cycle had longer
508 EPSP-to-AP transition times than events that occurred later in the cycle. For further analysis,
509 all triggered *PEA* complexes were split at the median EPSP-to-AP transition time into two
510 groups, one with slower (EPSP_{slow}, blue circle, Fig. 10C inset, same data as in 10B) and one
511 with faster EPSP-to-AP transition times (EPSP_{fast}, red circles). Events of the EPSP_{slow} group
512 (blue solid line, Fig. 10C) were, on average, triggered earlier in the cycle than events of the
513 EPSP_{fast} group (red solid line). This contrasted with the AP time points in both groups which
514 showed almost homogeneous distributions (blue and red dashed lines). The distance of the
515 respective distributions (EPSP_{slow} vs EPSP_{fast} and AP_{slow} vs AP_{fast}) was assessed by calculating
516 the Jenson-Shannon distance (JSD, Rao, 1982; Wong and You, 1985; Lin and Wong, 1990).
517 In 91.3% of the recordings (21/23), the JSD between AP groups was smaller than between the
518 respective EPSP groups (JSD_{EPSP} = 0.015 ± 0.012 vs. JSD_{AP} = 0.004 ± 0.006 , $p < 0.001$,
519 $U1 = 0.09$, $n = 23$, Fig. 10D), suggesting that the variability in EPSP-to-AP transition time fa-
520 cilitates precise SBC spiking.

521 However, varying EPSP-to-AP transition times can only be functionally linked to precisely
522 phase-locked APs, if just EPSPs that are leading the preferred phase are affected. EPSPs lag-
523 ging behind the preferred phase should be precluded from triggering an AP. To test for this, we
524 analyzed the phase position of *PE* complexes within the stimulus period relative to the overall
525 ANF input (Fig. 10E). As before, the ANF input was set to be centered on 180° (*PEA+PE*,

526 black lines, inset showing period histograms for an exemplary cell). In relation to this distribu-
527 tion, the incidence of *PE* complexes (red lines, see also inset) were shifted to larger phase
528 angles, i.e. EPSPs that arrive after the preferred phase are less likely to generate an AP. In all
529 recorded cells, the incidence of *PE* complexes (red lines, Fig. 10E) was lagging the preferred
530 phase of the ANF input (black lines, ANF = 180° vs. PE = $210 \pm 16^\circ$, $p < 0.001$, paired *t*-test,
531 U1 = 0.98, n = 23).

532 Above, it was shown that the effect of inhibition depends on stimulus intensity which suggests
533 to test whether the improvement of temporal precision is also stimulus-dependent which would
534 provide additional evidence that inhibition has an immediate effect on the quality of phase
535 locking. Indeed, the comparison of phase locking between stimulation at low SPL (5–10 dB
536 above threshold) and at high SPL (40–50 dB above threshold) yielded a substantial improve-
537 ment in the high-SPL condition (low SPL = 0.03 ± 0.01 vs. high SPL = 0.06 ± 0.02 , ,
538 $p < 0.001$, paired *t* test, U1 = 0.71, n = 7, Fig. 10F).

539

540 *Iontophoretic application of glycine resembles the effects of inhibitory stimulation*

541 In vitro studies suggest a predominant role of glycinergic inhibition in the central auditory
542 system (Moore and Caspary, 1983; Caspary et al., 1994, 2008; Friauf et al., 2011; Nerlich et
543 al., 2014). To evaluate these findings and to test for the impact of glycinergic inhibition in vivo,
544 glycine was applied iontophoretically (100 mM, pH 6) with increasing current steps while re-
545 cording spontaneous activity of SBCs (n = 6). Glycine increased the incidence of *PE* signals
546 (red arrowheads Fig. 11A and red line in Fig. 11B) and reversibly reduced the number of *PEA*
547 signals (black stars and black line in Fig. 11A and B, respectively, $p < 0.001$, RM ANOVA,
548 Greenhouse-Geisser corrected, $\eta^2 = 0.68$, failure fraction: control = $25.9 \pm 18.7\%$ vs. applica-
549 tion = $76.1 \pm 20\%$, $p < 0.001$, control vs. recovery = $26.7 \pm 19.2\%$, $p = 0.79$, n = 6). Still, the

550 overall EPSP input to the SBC was not changed (Fig. 11B) ($p = 0.34$, RM ANOVA, $\eta^2 = 0.04$,
551 control = 69.5 ± 16.2 Hz vs. application = 66.4 ± 18 Hz, $n = 6$, data not shown). The increase
552 in failure fraction was directly correlated with the iontophoretic current reflecting the amount
553 of glycine applied ($r_s = 0.89$, $p < 0.05$, Fig. 11C). Glycine was potent enough to completely
554 block the postsynaptic activity in all recorded cells, when high enough currents were used.
555 Application of the carrier alone (20 mM NaCl, pH 6) did not affect the input firing rate (con-
556 trol = 71.5 ± 9.2 Hz vs. application = 72.8 ± 12.4 Hz, $p = 0.29$, RM ANOVA, $\eta^2 = 0.015$,
557 $n = 6$) or the proportion of *PE* and *PEA* signals (failure fraction: control = $22.3 \pm 11.3\%$ vs.
558 application = $23.3 \pm 12.6\%$, $p = 0.32$, RM ANOVA, $\eta^2 = 0.002$, $n = 6$, data not shown). In ad-
559 dition to affecting the reliability of signal transmission, glycine shaped the remaining APs in a
560 way similar to the changes observed during inhibitory acoustic stimulation (Fig. 11D). The
561 EPSP-AP transition time was prolonged during glycine application (left, $p < 0.001$, RM
562 ANOVA, $\eta^2 = 0.45$, control = 245 ± 9 μ s vs. application = 273 ± 14 μ s, $p < 0.001$, $n = 6$) and
563 the EPSP rising slopes were flattened (right, $p < 0.01$, RM ANOVA, $\eta^2 = 0.04$, con-
564 trol = 3.46 ± 1.03 V/s vs. application = 3.1 ± 0.95 V/s, $n = 6$). Both effects were reversible
565 within seconds (EPSP-AP: control vs. recovery = 248 ± 10 μ s, $p = 0.61$; EPSP slope: control
566 vs. recovery = 3.35 ± 0.93 V/s, $p = 0.64$), and none of these effects was observed while apply-
567 ing the carrier (20 mM NaCl, pH 6) alone (EPSP-AP transition time: control = 247 ± 10 μ s vs.
568 application = 250 ± 9 μ s, $p = 0.47$, RM ANOVA, $\eta^2 = 0.02$, $n = 6$; EPSP slopes: con-
569 trol = 2.98 ± 1.7 V/s vs. application = 2.93 ± 1.4 V/s, $p = 0.72$, RM ANOVA, $\eta^2 = 0.003$,
570 $n = 6$). These data suggest that glycine alone can, to a great extent, mimic the effect of acous-
571 tically evoked inhibition, which is in accordance with the suggested function of glycinergic
572 inhibition reported by in vitro studies.

573

574

575 **Discussion**

576 Earlier *in vivo* studies analyzed specific features of the juxtacellularly recorded signals to gain
577 insight into the underlying physiological processes of generation of AP discharges and synaptic
578 transmission at giant calyx terminals (Lorteije et al., 2009; Tolnai et al., 2009; Typlt et al.,
579 2010; Kuenzel et al., 2011; Sonntag et al., 2011). The present study provides a substantiation
580 of the analysis by focusing on the effects of dynamic interrelations between acoustically evoked
581 excitation and inhibition on the generation of APs by spherical bushy cells (SBCs).

582 The analysis was based on the relation of the different constituents of the neuronal three-com-
583 ponent voltage signals under distinctively different input conditions. Additionally, dynamic
584 changes in the units' discharge activity were assessed at the respective input conditions allow-
585 ing for an analysis of onset and offset of acoustically evoked excitation and inhibition.

586

587 *SBCs are target of inhibitory inputs*

588 Besides excitatory ANF input, SBCs receive inhibitory inputs mediated by GABA and/or gly-
589 cine (Wu and Oertel, 1986; Kolston et al., 1992; Juiz et al., 1996; Mahendrasingam et al., 2004;
590 Nerlich et al., 2014). Confirming the physiological impact of inhibitory inputs on SBCs, also
591 the presence of glycine and GABA receptors have been reported (Wenthold et al., 1988;
592 Campos et al., 2001). The highest density of inhibitory inputs was found at the rostral pole of
593 the AVCN (Moore and Moore, 1987; Kolston et al., 1992), the primary location of low-fre-
594 quency SBCs and target area of the present recordings. The impact of inhibition in different
595 SBCs might vary, since this morphologically and physiologically defined class of neurons is
596 the starting point of different afferent processing pathways.

597 *Low reliability of ANF-SBC signal transmission in vivo*

598 The juxtacellular recordings of SBCs reported here exhibit three-component waveforms with
599 a significant number of events lacking the third component. As shown by Typlt et al. (2010),
600 these three components reflect (i) the action potential of the endbulb of Held, frequently named
601 ‘prepotential’, (ii) the EPSP, and (iii) the postsynaptic AP, respectively. Without exception, the
602 prepotentials and the EPSPs occur together (*PE*), and these signals can be clearly distinguished
603 from the signal complexes additionally followed by the postsynaptic action potential (*PEA*).

604 These facts allows for an *in vivo* investigation of SBCs’ input-output functions using acoustic
605 stimulation (Englitz et al., 2009; Typlt et al., 2010; Kuenzel et al., 2011). The sum of *PE* and
606 *PEA* components indicate the ANF input to the SBC and the characteristics of acoustic re-
607 sponses are in agreement with previous studies in terms of rate-level function, maximum dis-
608 charge activity, threshold, and the presence of primary-like PSTH patterns (Schmiedt, 1989;
609 Winter et al., 1990; Ohlemiller et al., 1991; Müller, 1996). The *PE* complexes taken as such
610 indicate an ANF input that fails to trigger postsynaptic APs, while the *PEA* complexes indicate
611 the input spikes together with the postsynaptic APs. As observed earlier (Pfeiffer, 1966; Englitz
612 et al., 2009; Kuenzel et al., 2011), also in the absence of any acoustic stimulation the afferent
613 ANF activity does not reliably trigger APs in SBCs. Postsynaptic spike failures were observed
614 in about one-quarter of the signals of a unit, and the respective failure rates stayed constant
615 during stimulation outside the units’ acoustic response areas.

616 There are two possible causes for postsynaptic AP failures: (i) inhibitory interneurons exert a
617 respective effect and suppress AP generation, or (ii) SBCs are throughout in a partially de-
618 pressed state and the excitatory input operates close to the threshold of spike elicitation
619 (Kuenzel et al., 2011; Nerlich et al., 2014). The latter might be due to depletion of readily
620 releasable vesicles and sodium channel inactivation (Azouz and Gray, 2000; Henze and

621 Buzsáki, 2001; Wang and Manis, 2008; Yang and Xu-Friedman, 2008; Englitz et al., 2009;
622 Platkiewicz and Brette, 2010; Kuenzel et al., 2011).

623 We would like to argue that the major cause of spontaneous spike failures is depression. Our
624 unit sample was biased towards mid-to-high spontaneous activity and under these conditions
625 stochastic fluctuations of the release of excitatory transmitters result in EPSPs which differ in
626 amplitude, the small ones of which fail to trigger an AP (Wang and Manis, 2008; Yang and
627 Xu-Friedman, 2009; Wang et al., 2010; Kuenzel et al., 2011). Still, inhibition cannot a priori
628 be ruled out as a cause of spontaneous SBC spike failures, but there are several observations
629 that let it appear an unlikely option. Previously suggested candidates which might provide such
630 inhibition, the AVCN D-stellate cells and tuberculoventral cells of the DCN (Campagnola and
631 Manis, 2014), show low spontaneous discharge activity (Young and Brownell, 1976; Young
632 and Voigt, 1982; Rhode and Smith, 1986; Davis et al., 1996), suggesting that the influence of
633 inhibition will be limited under spontaneous activity. More importantly, local iontophoretic
634 application of strychnine during the recoding of spontaneous activity did not increase the rate
635 of postsynaptic APs directly indicating that the rate of spontaneous AP discharges is not limited
636 by inhibition.

637 *Effect of inhibition on SBCs acoustically triggered input-output function*

638 Based on *in vivo* recordings under the condition of acoustic stimulation, earlier studies reported
639 an impact of GABA and glycine on SBCs' tuning properties (Caspary et al., 1994; Gai and
640 Carney, 2008; Dehmel et al., 2010) and on temporal precision of AP discharges (Dehmel et al.,
641 2010). The effect of inhibition becomes also apparent from the SBCs' non-monotonic RLFs
642 (Winter and Palmer, 1991; Kopp-Scheinflug et al., 2002) and from the increase in the preci-
643 sion of AP phase locking to low-frequency tone bursts compared to ANF recordings (Rothman
644 et al., 1993; Joris et al., 1994b; Burkitt and Clark, 1999).

645 Since auditory nerve fibers are solely excitatory, the observed inhibitory influence requires the
646 contribution of inhibitory interneurons, possibly from within the CN, e.g. AVCN D-stellate
647 cells and/or tuberculoventral cells of the DCN, which directly or indirectly receive ANF input
648 (Wickesberg and Oertel, 1990; Saint Marie et al., 1991; Campagnola and Manis, 2014). An-
649 other possibility would be a back-projection from periolivary nuclei, e.g. the lateral nucleus of
650 the trapezoid body which receives input from the AVCN (Smith et al., 1991; Schofield and
651 Cant, 1992). Currently available data do not allow a differentiation between either of these
652 options. However, tuberculoventral cells show onset responses and non-monotonic rate-level
653 functions (Rhode, 1999), and D-stellate are characterized by transient chopper-onset responses
654 (Oertel et al., 1990; Paolini and Clark, 1999). Thus, both neuron types within the CN cannot
655 fully account for the level-dependent, tonic inhibition observed in SBCs in vivo.

656 The initial characterization of each unit's response areas enabled the establishment of stimulus
657 conditions under which the sole effects of acoustically evoked inhibition could be observed.
658 Setting the stimulus frequency to the units' inhibitory response areas guaranteed a steady (spon-
659 taneous) excitatory input and allowed to quantify the acoustically evoked inhibitory effects on
660 SBC discharges. This is evidenced by the fact that under these conditions the overall excitatory
661 input to the SBC ($PE + PEA$) remained constant before, during and after the respective tone-
662 burst stimulation (Figs. 5 and 6). Despite such constant input, the AP rates show a clear stim-
663 ulus-evoked reduction characterized by delayed onset and offset. These findings are consistent
664 with previous studies, that showed long latency of IPSPs in brain slice (Wu and Oertel, 1986)
665 and in vivo (Paolini and Clark, 1998) as well as slow dynamics of IPSCs in SBCs (Xie and
666 Manis, 2013; Nerlich et al., 2014) resulting in a built-up of inhibitory conductance during stim-
667 ulation.

668 *Increase in temporal precision at the level of the SBCs*

669 The presently observed increase in phase locking from the ANF to the SBC output is consistent
670 with previous reports (Joris et al., 1994a, 1994b; Paolini et al., 2001; Dehmel et al., 2010;
671 Kuenzel et al., 2011) and similar data have recently been reported for hair cell synapses (Li et
672 al., 2014). While Kuenzel et al. (2011) reported that the variability in EPSP-to-AP transition
673 time degrades or at best conserves the temporal precision, the present analysis yielded a signif-
674 icant two-step improvement of phase locking at the SBC output: the first by the selection of
675 well-timed EPSPs and the second from the shift of the AP towards the preferred stimulus phase.
676 The second step might reflect the involvement of additional non-endbulb excitatory ANF in-
677 puts to SBCs the functional role of which still remains elusive (Ryugo and Sento, 1991; Young
678 and Sachs, 2008; Gómez-Nieto and Rubio, 2009; Cao and Oertel, 2010; Lauer et al., 2013).
679 Based on the analysis exemplified in Fig. 10, we would like to bring forward the idea that in
680 low-frequency SBCs the input from partially depressed somatic endbulbs (Kuenzel et al., 2011)
681 interacts with dendritic excitatory inputs arising from auditory-nerve branches (Gómez-Nieto
682 and Rubio, 2009). The latter would create phase-locked oscillations of the membrane potential
683 on top of which just well-timed endbulb EPSPs are capable of generating a postsynaptic AP
684 (Kuenzel, 2015; Kuenzel et al., 2015). At higher sound levels also the impact of inhibition
685 increases, which tightens the condition for AP elicitation guaranteeing consistent phase lock-
686 ing. Thus, although slow, this acoustically evoked inhibition might dynamically alter the input-
687 output function and substantially increase the temporal precision in a time-sensitive neuronal
688 circuit.

689

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- 908
- 909

910 **Figure legends**

911 **Figure 1:** Juxtacellular recordings of SBCs show two types of signals. **A**, Representative volt-
912 age trace of an SBC's spontaneous activity display complex signal waveforms always consist-
913 ing of a prepotential (PP) and the excitatory postsynaptic potential (EPSP) which may (black
914 stars) or may not (black arrowheads) be followed by an action potential (AP). **B**, Superimposed
915 waveforms of 100 single events, **(left)** *PEA* composed of PP, EPSP, and AP, **(middle)** *PE*
916 composed of PP and EPSP. Both signal complexes originate from the same source as previ-
917 ously shown by Typlt et al. (2010). **(right)** The mean signal waveforms suggest that, while the
918 PP size stays constant, the EPSP strength is reduced in signals that lack the AP (inset, gray
919 line).

920

921 **Figure 2:** Frequency response areas (FRA) of auditory nerve input to the SBC and the resulting
922 afferent activity. **A**, Recorded voltage signals were decomposed in *PEA* (black) and *PE* (red)
923 with the sum of both indicating the auditory nerve input to the SBC **(B)**. The respective FRA
924 showed a v-shape frequency-intensity domain of excitation (CF: 1.9 kHz, threshold: -3 dB
925 SPL). **C**, FRA of the *PEA* signals of the same SBC showed reduced firing rates both within the
926 excitatory response area (84–154 spikes/s at the highest stimulus intensities and in most parts
927 of the excitatory response area) as well as in frequency-intensity ranges devoid of lacking any
928 discernable impact of stimulation (SP; e.g. mean spike rates 40–56 spikes/s across the entire
929 intensity range at 0.15 kHz). In a circumscribed frequency-intensity range on the high-fre-
930 quency side of the excitatory FRA, acoustic stimulation caused a considerable decrease in *PEA*
931 even below spontaneous rates, forming an inhibitory sideband. **D**, The decrease in *PEA*, i.e. in
932 postsynaptic firing, went along with a relative increase in *PE*, i.e. the failure fraction, especially

933 in the area of the inhibitory sideband, but to a certain extent also throughout the excitatory
934 FRA.

935

936 **Figure 3:** SBC discharges during repetitive acoustic stimulation outside the receptive field,
937 same unit as in Fig. 2. **A** (lower panel), During repetitive acoustic stimulation at 0.15 kHz,
938 50 dB SPL (mark on the 'Sp' line in Fig. 2) *PE* (red) and *PEA* (black) signal complexes were
939 both uncorrelated to the acoustic stimulus. Insets in the upper panel show blow-ups of stimulus
940 onset (left) and offset (right). **B**, Binned data from A (bin width 1 ms, moving average 3 ms).
941 The acoustic stimulus did not change the overall input to the SBC (gray line, *PE+PEA*) nor the
942 incidence of *PE* (red line) or *PEA* (black line). **C**, The probabilities of *PE* (red) and *PEA* (black)
943 were normalized to the overall input (gray). Probability of ANF input failing to trigger SBC
944 APs (red line) showed short-term fluctuations in the range of 0 to 0.3, but was not correlated
945 with the stimulus.

946

947 **Figure 4:** Responses to repetitive acoustic stimulation at unit's characteristic frequency
948 1.9 kHz, 30 dB SPL (marked by dot on the 'CF' line Fig. 2). **A**, Dotplot during repetitive CF
949 stimulation. Both *PE* (red) and *PEA* (black) signal complexes were present before and after the
950 stimulation. Stimulation at CF resulted in a considerable increase of both signal complexes
951 with increasing incidences of *PE* with ongoing stimulation. Blow-up of the discharge activity
952 at stimulus onset (upper panel, left) and offset (right) at CF stimulation. **B**, Binned data from
953 A; binwidth 1 ms, moving average 3 ms. Acoustic stimulation at the unit's CF increased the
954 overall input to the SBC (*PE + PEA*, gray line) as well as SBC spiking (*PEA*, black line). Both
955 display the typical primary-like response pattern. While *PE* modestly increased during the sus-
956 tained response phase, *PEA* showed slight reduction, matched by an increase in *PE* incidence

957 (red line). **C**, Probability of *PE* and *PEA* normalized to the overall input. Incidence of *PE* in-
958 creased gradually with ongoing stimulation and surpassed the AP probability 20 ms after stim-
959 ulus onset. Dashed lines indicate bins where less than five events occur and therefore probabilit-
960 ities were not calculated.

961

962 **Figure 5:** Response to repetitive acoustic stimulation within inhibitory sideband (4.8 kHz,
963 50 dB SPL; dot on the 'Inh' line in Fig. 2. **A (lower panel)**, Dotplot of *PEA* (black) and *PE*
964 (red) during repetitive acoustic stimulation. This graph and the blow-ups of activity at stimulus
965 onset (upper panel, left) and offset (upper panel, right) indicate that while the overall activity
966 is not altered by the stimulus, the ratio between *PE* and *PEA* is shifted towards higher incidence
967 of *PE*. **B**, Binned data from A elucidates sustained overall input activity (gray line, *PE* + *PEA*),
968 but considerably increased failure rates (red line, *PE*) during stimulation, which is in contrast
969 to the concurrent reduction of postsynaptic APs (black line, *PEA*). **C**, Probability of *PE* and
970 *PEA* normalized to the overall input (*PE* + *PEA*). Reduction in postsynaptic APs (black) is
971 matched with respect to dimension and temporal dynamics by an increase in AP failures (red).

972

973 **Figure 6:** Averaged data of 16 to 23 cells. **A**, Acoustic stimulation (100 ms, black icon on top
974 of the graph) outside the receptive field did not change the auditory nerve input to the SBC
975 ($n = 18$; gray line, upper panel) nor altered the proportion between *PEA* (black line, lower
976 panel) and *PE* (red line). The average failure fraction of about one quarter was uncorrelated
977 with the acoustic stimulation. **B**, CF stimulation resulted in an excitatory primary-like response
978 pattern of the auditory nerve input (*PE*) to the SBCs ($n = 16$; gray, upper panel). In the course
979 of excitatory acoustic stimulation, the probability of AP generation (black, lower panel) de-
980 creased and AP failure fraction increased (red). **C**, Acoustic stimulation within the inhibitory
981 sideband did not alter the ANF input to the SBCs ($n = 23$; gray, *PE* + *PEA*, upper panel), but

982 considerably changed the PE/PEA ratio; the failure fraction increased from 25.3% to 58.9% on
983 average. ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, paired t test

984

985 **Figure 7:** Comparison of onset and offset dynamics of acoustically evoked inhibition and ex-
986 citation. Mean values (thick red line, $n = 23$) and failure fractions from individual units (thin
987 red lines) are shown and contrasted with the average AP firing upon CF stimulation (black line,
988 right ordinate, $n = 16$). Units showed slow inhibitory onset dynamics (lower left panel, half-
989 rise time 8.4 ms) compared to the faster increase in AP firing during CF stimulation (black line,
990 HRT = 4 ms). After the end of stimulation (lower right panel), the failure fraction decayed
991 slower ($\tau = 9.38$ ms) for stimulation in the inhibitory sideband than AP firing at the offset of
992 CF stimulation ($\tau = 0.86$ ms).

993

994 **Figure 8:** Rate level functions of ANF input and SBC firing at different frequencies (same unit
995 as in Fig. 2). **A**, RLFs of SBC input ($PE + PEA$) neither showed changes in firing rate outside
996 of the receptive field (short dashed line, 'Sp' in Fig. 2) nor for stimulation within the inhibitory
997 sideband (long dashed line; 'Inh' in Fig. 2). The firing rate at the unit's CF increased mono-
998 tonically up to 35 dB SPL and flattened towards higher SPLs (solid line, 'CF' in Fig. 2). **B**,
999 RLF of AP rates (PEA) showed overall decreased activity for all stimulus conditions. Still, as
1000 for the input activity the rates did not vary with intensity outside the unit's response area (short
1001 dashed line). At CF the RLF had a non-monotonic course (solid line), and stimulation within
1002 the inhibitory sideband increasingly reduced rates above 25 dB SPL (long dashed line, 'Inh' in
1003 Fig. 2). **C**, Respective failure fractions were calculated as $PE/(PE + PEA)$. The decrease in
1004 SBC AP rates as compared to the ANF input is accompanied by an increase in failure fraction
1005 at CF as well as the inhibitory sideband. Note that for inhibitory sideband stimulation the in-
1006 crease of failure fraction occurs at lower intensities than that of CF stimulation and the overall

1007 effect was larger. **D**, SBC firing and failure fraction with increasing stimulus intensity at the
1008 inhibitory sideband. Data of 23 units. Units differed in their spontaneous AP rates and failure
1009 fraction (gray lines; 0 dB in left and right panel). Still, with increasing stimulus intensity AP
1010 rates decreased (left panel) (mean $r_s = 0.7$, $p < 0.001$, black line) and failure fraction increased
1011 in all units (right panel) ($r_s = -0.59$, $p < 0.001$, mean: black line).

1012

1013 **Figure 9:** Inhibition flattened EPSP slopes and prolonged EPSP-AP transition times. **Ai**, Two
1014 representative single events with long (black) and short EPSP-AP transition time (gray) aligned
1015 at the prepotential. As indicated in the graph, the analysis quantifies the time from the peak of
1016 the EPSP or the respective inflection point of the EPSP rising slope to the peak of the AP. **Aii**,
1017 Representative cumulative distribution function of EPSP-AP transition times for spontaneous
1018 activity (light gray) and inhibitory stimulation (dark gray). The shape of the distribution re-
1019 mains unaltered, but inhibitory stimulation shifts the average transition time by 20 μ s (median)
1020 towards higher values. **Aiii**, In all analyzed cells inhibitory stimulation increased the median
1021 EPSP-AP transition time. **Bi**, Rising slope of EPSP as an indication of EPSP strength. Exam-
1022 ples show constant PP signals, but EPSP slopes varying with stimulus condition, spontaneous
1023 activity (gray) and inhibitory stimulation (black). **Bii**, Inhibitory stimulation shifted the cumu-
1024 lative distribution function by 0.16 V/s (median) towards lower values, indicating a reduced
1025 EPSP strength. **Biii**, Stimulus evoked reduction in EPSP rising slopes were observed in 19 out
1026 of 23 cells. ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

1027

1028 **Figure 10:** Transformation of phase locking accuracy in SBCs. **A**, Vector strength of ANF,
1029 EPSPs, and APs for 23 different units. The temporal precision is improved at the level of suc-
1030 cessful EPSPs and their subsequent APs. **B**, for *PEA* complexes the EPSP-to-AP transition time
1031 was negatively correlated with the EPSP time point within the stimulus cycle, i.e. signals that

1032 occurred early in the phase had longer EPSP-to-AP transition times. The black line represents
1033 the median trend line **C**, For each recording, the data set was split at the respective median of
1034 EPSP-to-AP transition times to form two groups of *PEA* complexes, one with slow (blue) and
1035 one with fast (red) EPSP-to-AP transition times (see inset). While the EPSP time points of
1036 events of the EPSP_{slow} group occurred, on average, earlier in the cycle than the ones of the
1037 EPSP_{fast} group (solid lines), the time points of the respective APs were much more overlapping
1038 (dashed lines). **D**, The divergence of EPSP and AP time points of both groups was assessed by
1039 calculating the Jensen-Shannon distance and yielded a substantial increase in overlap in AP
1040 time points compared to EPSP time points across the two groups. **E**, The period histogram of
1041 the ANF input (black) was centered at 180° and the incidence of *PE* complexes relative to this
1042 position analyzed (red, inset showing exemplary cell). The cumulative distribution of ANF
1043 (black, thin lines = single cells, thick line = mean of single cells) and *PE* (red lines) occurrence
1044 within the stimulus period revealed that the incidence of *PE* complexes in all cells lagged the
1045 ANF input, i.e. EPSPs occurring after the preferred phase are unlikely to generate an AP . **F**,
1046 Acoustically stimulation at high SPL (40–50 dB above threshold) resulted in a larger improve-
1047 ment of AP timing than low-SPL stimulation (5–10 dB above threshold), *** $p < 0.001$

1048

1049 **Figure 11:** Effect of iontophoretic glycine application on spontaneous activity. **A**, Both action
1050 potentials (*PEA*, black star) and *PE* (red arrowheads) are present under control conditions (up-
1051 per trace). Iontophoretic application of glycine changed the *PEA/PE* ratio, i.e. more EPSPs
1052 failed to trigger an AP (middle trace). This effect was reversible with the *PEA/PE* ratio turning
1053 back to pre-application conditions (lower trace). **B**, Binned data of **A**. The overall input rate
1054 (*PE* + *PEA*, gray line, left ordinate) remained constant during glycine application. The failure
1055 fraction (red line, right ordinate) increased during application on the expenses of a decreased

1056 AP probability (black line). **C**, Failure fraction increase upon glycine application was corre-
1057 lated to the iontophoretic current used, i.e. the amount of glycine ejected. **D**, Application of
1058 glycine did also affect the waveform of remaining APs. Similar to acoustic stimulation the
1059 EPSP-AP transition time was prolonged (left) and the EPSP slopes flattened (right) during
1060 application. The magnitude of the effect resembled the inhibitory sideband stimulation, dashed
1061 lines indicate cumulative distribution from Fig. 9B.

1062

Keine & Rübssamen, Fig. 1

A

B

C

D

Keine & Rübsem, Fig. 3

Keine & RübSamen, Fig. 4

Keine & RübSamen, Fig. 5

Keine & RübSamen, Fig. 7

Keine & RübSamen, Fig. 9

